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Ranking of Countries by Voice and Accountability

Between 2013 and 2021, the value of Voice and Accountability grew by an average of 25.53%

Voice and Accountability captures perceptions of the extent to which a country's citizens are able to participate in the selection of their government, as well as freedom of expression, freedom of association and freedom of the media. The estimate gives the country's score on the aggregate indicator, in units of a standard normal distribution, i.e. ranging from approximately -2.5 to 2.5.

Ranking of countries by value of Voice and Accountability in 2021. Norway ranks first in value of Voice and Accountability in 2021 with a value of 1.75, followed by Finland and New Zealand with a value of 1.62, the Denmark with an amount of 1.56, and from Switzerland with an amount of 1.55 units. In the middle of the table are Armenia with a value of 0.06 units, Moldova with an amount of 0.05 units, Papua New Guinea with 0.02 units, Georgia with 0.02 units, Paraguay with 0.01 units and Lesotho with -0.02 units. The ranking is closed by Somalia -1.75, followed by Turkmenistan with a value of -1.91 units, by Syria with -1.92 units, by Eritrea with a value of -1.93 units and by North Korea with an amount of -2.07 units.

Ranking of countries by value of percentage change in Voice and Accountability between 2013 and 2021. Solomon Islands ranks first in percentage growth rate in value of Voice and Accountability between 2013 and 2021 with a value equal to 30,740, 84%, followed by Seychelles with 3,082.91%, Guyana with 1,062.01%, Papua New Guinea with 614.44%, Timor Leste with 403.79%. In the middle of the table are Norway with an amount of 0.79%, followed by Barbados with a value of 0.44%, followed by Canada with a value of -0.3 units, China with a value of -0, 32%, followed by the Bahamas with a value of -1.15%, and by Lao PDR with a value of -1.96. The ranking is closed by Tanzania with a value of -249.2%, Benin with -252.76%, El Salvador with a value of 321.88%, Singapore with -470.05%, the Philippines with a value of -2.471.12%.

Machine Learning and Predictions. Machine learning algorithms are applied below for predicting the future value of the Voice and Accountability variable. The algorithms are analyzed on the basis of their ability to maximize the R-Squared and to minimize the value of the statistical errors MAE, MSE, RMSE. The algorithms were trained with 80% of the data while the remaining 20% was used for the actual prediction. The following ordering of orders is thus determined, namely:

- Polynomial Regression with a payoff value equal to 11 units;
- Linear Regression and Random Forest Regression with a payoff value equal to 13;
- Gradient Boosted Tree with a payoff value of 15;
- Tree Ensemble Regression with a payoff value of 17;
- Simple Regression Tree with a payoff value of 21;
- ANN-Artificial Neural Network with a payoff value of 25;
- PNN-Probabilistic Neural Network with a payoff value of 29.

It therefore follows that Polynomial Regression is the algorithm with the greatest predictive capacity in terms of reducing the value of statistical errors and maximizing the R-squared. Based on whether

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the algorithm predicts a growth or a reduction in the value of Voice and Accountability, it is possible to distinguish the countries between winners and losers.

Winning countries. Based on the application of the Polynomial Regression algorithm, it is possible to predict a growth in the value of Voice and Accountability for the following countries, namely:

- South Sudan with a growth equal to an amount of 16.68%;
- Fiji with pear growth at a value of 15.83%;
- Benin with a predicted growth of 5.44%;
- Haiti with a growth of 4.27%;
- Hungary with a growth equal to an amount of 3.95%;
- Bolivia with a growth equal to an amount of 3.05%;
- Turkey with a growth equal to an amount of 2.96%;
- Botswana with a predicted value of 1.81%;
- Kazakhstan with growth equal to a value of 1.73%;
- Malta with a growth equal to a value of 1.61%;
- Mexico with a growth equal to a value of 1.15%;
- St Vincent and the Grenadines with a growth of +1.04%;
- Finland with a growth of 0.25%;
- Switzerland with a growth of 0.05%.

Losing countries. The algorithm also predicts a reduction in the value of Voice and Accountability for some countries. In particular, the countries for which a reduction in the value of Voice and Accountability is predicted are indicated below:

- Monaco with a value of -0.03%;
- Norway with a value of -0.11%;
- India with a value of -0.19%;
- Jordan with a value of -0.8%;
- Denmark with a value of -0.99%;
- Lithuania with a value of -1.07%;
- Cabo Verde with -1.28%;
- Japan with a value of -2.07%;
- The Gambia with a value of -2.23%;
- Comoros with a value of -2.5%;
- Sierra Leone with a value of -2.65%;
- Burkina Faso with a value of -2.78%;
- Papua New Guinea with a value of -3.15%;
- Tonga with a value of -3.33%;
- Vanuatu with a value of -4.31%;
- Azerbaijan with a value of -5.16%;
- Mali with a value of -6.01%;
- Uzbekistan with a value of -7.00%;
- Tanzania with a value of -8.01%;
- United Arab Emirates with a value of -9.05%;
- Mauritania with a value of -12.94%;
- Vietnam with a value of -13.45%;
- Iran Islamic Republic with a value of -19.23%;
- Lao PDR with a value of -24.24%.

Conclusions. The value of Voice and Accountability grew on average in all the countries considered between 2013 and 2021 by +25.53%. Certainly, the value of Voice and Accountability is high within the Western world. However, there are also other areas of the world where the value of Voice and Accountability is growing, i.e. Latin America, where the values are positive except in the case of Venezuela, Southern Africa, and some Asian countries, i.e. India, Mongolia and South East Asia. It should be considered that the growth in the value of Voice and Accountability could also be connected to the development of the Internet and online communications, which have increased knowledge of political facts and increased the possibility of citizens to actively participate in the democratic and institutional life of their country. However, there are still many areas worldwide where the value of Voice and Accountability is low and among these Russia, almost all of central-northern Africa, China, the Middle East and central Asia stand out.. It is clear that the possibility of accessing democratic participation in political and institutional life essentially depends on the possibility of living in democratic regimes capable of protecting freedom of expression.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Funding. The authors received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration of Competing Interest. The authors declare that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

Acknowledgements. We are grateful to the teaching staff of the LUM University “Giuseppe Degennaro” and to the management of the LUM Enterprise s.r.l. for the constant inspiration to continue our scientific research work undeterred.

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Appendix

Statistical Errors				
	R ²	mean absolute error	mean squared error	root mean squared error
ANN	0,9808653	0,0364837	0,0020129	0,0448650
PNN	0,9714716	0,0432290	0,0030010	0,0547817
Simple Regression Tree	0,9862726	0,0276878	0,0014440	0,0380006
Gradient Boosted Tree	0,9934421	0,0200057	0,0100000	0,0262652
Random Forest Regression	0,9895722	0,0253649	0,0010969	0,0331201
Tree Ensemble Regression	0,9892581	0,0263298	0,0011300	0,0336154
Linear Regression	0,9935128	0,0165212	0,0100000	0,0229789
Polynomial Regression	0,9936680	0,0164549	0,0100000	0,0229713

Ranking of Algorithms based on predictive efficiency					
Algoritmo	R ²	mean absolute error	mean squared error	root mean squared error	Sum
<i>Polynomial Regression</i>	1	1	8	1	11
<i>Linear Regression</i>	2	2	7	2	13
<i>Gradient Boosted Tree</i>	3	3	6	3	15
<i>Random Forest Regression</i>	4	4	1	4	13
<i>Tree Ensemble Regression</i>	5	5	2	5	17
<i>Simple Regression Tree</i>	6	6	3	6	21
ANN	7	7	4	7	25
PNN	8	8	5	8	29